

The proceedings of the workshop were initiated by K. S. Jauhri of the host institute who spoke about the activities, expertise of research, business opportunities and transnational alliances of IIP. This was followed by a brief description of the workshop and its various technical sessions by M. O. Garg. The first lecture was delivered by A. K. Jain (EIL) who reviewed the recent advancements in the area of *N*-methyl pyrrolidone, i.e. NMP process technology. He opined that researchers should continuously optimize the existing processing units and incorporate newer developments. B. S. Rawat giving a presentation on the applications of solvent extraction in petroleum and petrochemicals industry covered the current status of this technique in Indian refineries. M. Anwar (IIP) discussed the market trends in hydroprocessed base oil and outlined the various steps involved in evaluation and processing of crudes for lube oil base stock production.

In another lecture, A. K. Jain addressed more recent technological methods based on the desirable properties of solvent for lube extraction. He also highlighted the key problems which

are currently envisaged in this area. That feed stock for lube oil base stock can be produced through vacuum distillation of atmospheric residue or propane deasphalting of vacuum residue as was demonstrated by the presentation of G. S. Dang (IIP). In another lecture, M. O. Garg (IIP) while highlighting the importance of solvent extraction in hydrocarbon industry, discussed the basic principles of process engineering for constructing large-scale packed liquid-liquid extractor. He also reviewed the recent trends in lube extraction in the context of Indian refineries. In a joint presentation, M. Anwar and A. K. Jain talked about the experiences of their respective institutes with R&D advancements in the area of lube oil base stock production through NMP process. The last lecture of the workshop was by K. S. Balaraman (Madras Refinery Limited) in which he stated that all new technologies must meet the future lube base oil quality requirements.

Later in a distinguished lecture delivered by P. K. Mukhopadhyay (Consultant, IIP and EIL), a presentation on the recent trends in production of lube base oil was given. He said that there is

an increasing trend towards improvement in base oil quality to facilitate manufacture of superior lubricants. There is a big demand on energy efficient multi-grade oils and Indian refineries could make a dent in this area, he said. He also discussed the various hydrogen processing operations employed in lube base oil production.

On the concluding day there was a panel discussion which included proposals from participants with respect to future course of action. Though the proceedings showed that much emphasis was directed towards exploitation of technology rather than fundamental research, the consensus opinion expressed at the meeting was that this is bound to produce many synergistic effects in the future. The stimulating discussions, the newer ideas and the friendly interaction will remain longer in the memories of participants.

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Science Summit*

Fifty years after Independence, despite some success stories, all is not well with Indian science. That was the impression one got listening to the talks and discussions at the Science Summit.

The chairman of the meet, C. N. R. Rao, did not hide his unhappiness and anguish when he spoke about the indifference of the bureaucracy to science and the oppressive atmosphere in which scientific research was being carried out in the country. He was particularly unhappy, as was P. Balaram, about the enormous delays in getting funds released from the departments of the Ministry of Science and Technology for approved research projects. Even letters were not being replied to. If this could happen to him, what would be the fate of young scientists in the early years of their

careers, he wondered. I fully agree with him. Science moves so fast that such delays can render project proposals outdated. The costs of equipment could go up. Worse still, the investigator might lose interest. According to R. A. Mashelkar, Director General of CSIR, some Indian pharmaceutical companies were moving their research and development activities outside India because they wanted a hassle-free environment.

Both Rao and Balaram admitted that science did not attract bright students any more. V. C. Kulandaiswamy, who had been a Vice-Chancellor of three universities said that enrollment in science courses was shrinking. The quality of training offered by our universities is deteriorating. Two years ago, the Institute of Mathematical Sciences in Chennai could not find a single suitable candidate for their doctoral programme in mathematics. In his keynote talk at the

World Conference on Science held in June 1999 at Budapest, M. S. Swaminathan had pleaded for nurturing and fostering young research leaders who could both initiate and manage change. But, thanks to the policy of freezing new appointments, the average age of scientists in CSIR stood at fifty plus, said Mashelkar. At the Science Summit, where the youngest speaker was fifty and felt 'like a foot soldier in a gathering of generals', most speakers were above sixty. Even the average age of the audience must have been close to fifty. I wondered why younger speakers were not invited.

We are not investing enough on research, said P. Rama Rao, former secretary to the Government of India in the Department of Science and Technology (DST). Currently the figure is about 0.8% of GDP. He would like it to be around 2.0% of GDP. Japan, USA,

*Organized by the Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan at Bangalore during 7-8 August 1999.

France, Germany and the UK invest more than 2% of GDP on R&D. C. N. R. Rao pointed out that although the total science budget runs to a few thousand crore rupees, what was available for the kind of research carried out in academic institutions in physics, chemistry and mathematics was not more than Rs 50 crores. How then could we compete with the best in the world and be world leaders in at least a few areas, he asked. Balaram pointed out that much of the money went to mega applied projects, many of which would need a strong base of basic research. But once-glorious universities had been reduced to mere degree-granting institutions without any claim to excellence in research, he lamented. If universities are starved, where could laboratories go to find scientists to carry out serious scientific research? In his view, the engine of science was unmistakably slowing down in India. Kulandaiswamy gave plenty of statistics to show that the country was not investing enough on education at all levels and pleaded for an investment of at least 6% of GDP on education.

Much was said about bureaucracy's stranglehold on scientists, and the general consensus was in favour of appointing specialists rather than administrative cadre generalists. Satish Chandran, the only member of the IAS fraternity to speak at the Summit, agreed that specialists should be appointed in science departments. But he pointed out that the scientific community failed abysmally when the flexible complementation system was introduced to facilitate quick promotion of meritorious scientists. What actually happened was that virtually everyone, irrespective of merit or competence, was promoted to higher grades. Having worked for more than three decades in CSIR, and having observed other science departments for a long time, I am convinced that there are many in science who ought not to be there in the first place. For all we know, this lapse on the part of scientists could have caused a backlash among the generalist administrators and finance officers leading to the oppressive atmosphere mentioned by Rao. Besides, the delays are not caused always by bureaucrats. [For instance, it took more than a year for the scientists in the NSTMIS section of DST to inform one of

my colleagues that a proposal submitted by him was being transferred (without his prior consent) to NISSAT!]

Much of what is said here is known to most readers of *Current Science*. But what makes it important now is that it is all being acknowledged in an open forum by people who have held or are holding important positions in the S&T establishment of the country. That is a welcome change. Seventeen years ago, when a *New York Times* correspondent juxtaposed extensive quotes from an article I wrote in *Science Today* in 1975 with comments made by late Indira Gandhi at the annual meeting of the Indian Science Congress Association in 1982, the scientific establishment was not very kind to me. More recently, when Madhavi and Raghuram pointed out in a note in *Nature* that science in India, in terms of number of papers published in journals, was declining, they faced a rough time. But alone among the top brass in Indian science, C. N. R. Rao has been saying for several years that science in India is not doing well, and that Indian researchers find it increasingly difficult to publish their work in important journals of the world, especially in experimental sciences.

Swaminathan admirably brought out the need for science to solve the pressing problems of the people. In the years to come, he warned that we would need to produce far larger quantities of food from smaller area of arable land and dwindling water resources to feed the growing population, both human and animal. He emphasized the need to preserve and document the country's rich biodiversity, need to bring about gender equity and higher levels of nutrition. He was greatly concerned that despite major innovations in science and technology, poverty, malnutrition, illiteracy, gender and social inequity continued to plague the world. This was simply indefensible. He suggested that there were uncommon opportunities to harness the awesome power of science and technology to make the world a better place to live in, but it required bringing about a high level of synergy between science and public policy. Unless agriculture is made both economically rewarding and intellectually satisfying, Swaminathan said, it would be difficult to prevent the exodus of agriculture graduates migrating to

other more lucrative professions. Ashok Khosla of Development Alternatives, New Delhi, pointed out that less than 1% of the entire R&D budget of the country went to rural development. He described many eco-friendly and employment-generating technologies suitable for India.

Manju Sharma gave a progress report of achievements in biotechnology and literally brushed aside all criticism of genetically modified organisms. She challenged critics to show one instance where biotechnology had harmed people. Swaminathan, on the other hand, said that we should not ignore the people's concerns and that we should work for a new social contract between science and society. Kasturirangan narrated the successes of the Department of Space and Roddam Narasimha pointed out that the country had not realized its potential in the area of information technology. One would like to know what is happening to the Information Technology Task Force. Arcot Ramachandran spoke on the infrastructure needs, with emphasis on the energy needs of the country and the need for a high degree of professionalism. It was necessary to go beyond science and technology and to have a holistic perspective, he said.

If the meeting had ended with merely pointing out that all is not well with Indian science, it would only have saddened C. Subramaniam, the elder statesman, whose idea the summit was. The meeting did throw up a few suggestions. Rama Rao suggested that every department and ministry of the government should allocate a certain percentage of its allotted budget to R&D. For example, the Defence Ministry is allocating about 6% of its budget for research. He said that had the Railways invested even 1% of their revenue on R&D we would not have had so many accidents. Both Rama Rao and Balaram recommended that the Science and Engineering Research Council (SERC) of DST be made an autonomous body. Balaram went one step ahead: 'If science and scientists were getting a raw deal from government departments and the bureaucracy, then would it not be better to have an autonomous body of the kind of the National Research Council in Canada to oversee publicly funded research', he asked. Darbari Seth, the industrialist who has long been a friend

of scientific research in India, came up with a good suggestion: 'levy an R&D cess on industry and let the funds thus collected be managed by an independent body outside the government'. If this were to happen, paucity of funds for R&D would become a thing of the past. India could then be investing far more than 2% of GDP, suggested by Rama Rao, on R&D, as against 0.8% invested now. It also makes sense that the funds be administered by a non-governmental agency. Subramaniam suggested the formation of a national level corporation and several regional corporations for R&D, in which research laboratories, universities and industry could be partners. Such partnerships would ensure greater synergy and focus the country's R&D to problems of immediate relevance. One other suggestion was to establish a few commissions such as the Atomic Energy and Space Commissions, both of which have delivered the goods to a certain extent. But Raja Ramanna warned that some commissions, such as the Electronics Commission, had failed badly.

That most of the people who attended the meet stayed for all the sessions

shows how much regard they have for Subramaniam. He has played an important role in shaping scientific research in India. During his tenure as Minister for Agriculture we had the Green Revolution and during his tenure as Minister for Science and Technology the NCST came into being, which was later transformed into a full-fledged Department of Science and Technology. He had also contributed to the growth of DRDO when he was holding the Defence portfolio and was responsible for the introduction of remote sensing in India. Now at 90, he is keen to see that in the knowledge millennium science and technology should serve India well and should address and solve many of the problems that continue to plague the country.

What is the probability of the recommendations of the conference being translated into policy and action? This was essentially a meeting of scientists and science policy makers within the scientific community, with active participation of the secretaries of the Department of Scientific & Industrial Research and Department of Biotechnology, the Director General of the Indian Council of Medical

Research, the Chairman of the Space Commission, and the Chairman of the Atomic Energy Regulatory Board, apart from some very distinguished scientists. The secretary of the DST was to have attended but could not make it. But decisions on some of the recommendations have to be taken by the Government and the Parliament. In matters such as these, one's ability to strike a favourable deal with the individuals and institutions that can translate recommendations into policy and results is as important as having the ability to come up with the right recommendations in the first place. Luckily for us, science has not been unduly affected by party politics. Let us hope whichever party forms the government after the forthcoming election will pay heed to the recommendations of the summit.

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Science Summit* – Agenda for action

The agenda for action which constitutes the declaration released at the end of the recently concluded Science Summit in Bangalore is reproduced below.

– Editors

The Science Summit discussed a variety of crucial issues affecting science and technology (S&T) and national development. The challenges of the future are indeed formidable, demanding focused effort to meet them. We need to sharply tune our programmes in S&T to satisfy the minimum basic needs of the common man and promote sustainable development. We also need to concentrate on efforts in a few priority areas related to S&T, innovation and industrial

competitiveness, where India can create a global niche. India has to become a world leader at least in a few areas of basic sciences as well as technology. In addition, we have to satisfy the crucial infrastructural needs in areas such as energy, transportation and education. Out of such pragmatic efforts would emerge an India, which is economically sound and where social justice prevails. Much of the accomplishments would become possible only if the administration and management of science and of the country are thoroughly revamped. Some of the priority recommendations of the Summit are highlighted in this agenda for action.

Basic needs and sustainable development

A strategy for sustainable development will have to be worked out by having an integrated approach to planning, financing and management. Out of this should emerge programmes which provide not only the basic needs such as food, safe drinking water, shelter and so on, but also employment or livelihood opportunities particularly in the rural sector. All the programmes related to basic needs must clearly establish indicators of environmental, social and economic sustainability. It is necessary to form consortia of institutions in each eco-

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